

Lack of Absolute Time in Quantum Mechanics?

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Quantum mechanics seems to function at two levels in terms of probability. One level is represented by classical probabilities $P(x)=W^*(x)W(x)$ and $P(p)=a^*(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{wavefunction}=\sum_p a(p)\exp(ipx)$. For a free particle this level maps into continuous space and time i.e. $\exp(-iEt+ipx)*\exp(-iEt+ipx)=1$, but at a more fundamental level (the wavefunction level) there seems to be spatial and time resolution. Spatial resolution for a free particle is based on $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a resolution pattern $\cos(px)$ and its space shifted $\sin(px)$ representing motion. This resolution carries over to bound states for which $P(x)$ is not 1, but is represented by crests and troughs. $\exp(-iEt)$ represents resolution in time, we argue and is linked to $1/E$ where E is an energy associated with an interaction. As a result a bound system may have an overall $\exp(-i(M_1 + m_2 + E_n)t)$ where E_n is binding energy and an overall frequency (or spatial resolution of $1/(M_1 + m_2 + E_n)$, but $\exp(-iE_n t)$ represents a frequency of $1/E_n$ which is linked to the interaction between M_1 and m_2 . Thus the time resolution seems to be associated with energy and there may be various kinds of energy in a system (e.g. rest mass energy, binding energy) etc. These appear to be linked to different time resolutions. If E_n becomes 0, i.e. M_1 and m_2 no longer interact, then M_1 has a time resolution proportional to $1/M_1$ and m_2 , to $1/m_2$. Thus at the wavefunction level it does not seem there is an absolute time, rather there are various time resolutions associated with different energies.

Time and Spatial Resolution of a Free Particle

Classical mechanics considers a particle to be represented by a point i.e. its center-of-mass which may be at any x . Time is also continuous and there exists a relationship $x(t)$ from which one may calculate velocity acceleration etc. Quantum mechanics we argue is different in that it seems to imply that energy E and energy flow p are associated with resolution in time and space. This seems to imply a certain nonlocality associated with energy and momentum suggesting that not all x and t points have equal probability.

To link a free particle to the classical mechanical picture of continuous time and space, two sets of probability distributions are used i.e. one has 2 space: $\exp(-iEt) = \cos(Et) - i \sin(Et)$ and $\exp(ipx) = \cos(px) + i \sin(px)$. $\cos(px)$ represents a probability distribution showing wave motion as it evolves into its spatially shifted $\sin(px)$ and similar ideas hold for t . We argue that energy and energy flow itself are linked to such resolutions which become physically observable when interactions allowing for interference occur. For example an $\exp(ipx)$ free particle may interact with a two slit system (separated by a wavelength) and create an interference pattern showing spatial resolution explicitly.

This resolution, however, depends on what is identifiable in a problem e.g. what information exists. For example, consider a single particle bound system with a potential $V(x)$. One might argue that the potential knocks a free particle from one p to another, but then one would expect a distribution of $\sum_p a(p) \exp(-iEt+ipx)$, but $\sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is used instead. This suggests that p energy flow remains an identifiable quality of a particle, but its corresponding kinetic energy $pp/2m$ is not the full picture. In other words different single particle

energies do not determine the energy resolution when an interaction occurs. To see this more clearly consider the time-independent Schrodinger equation with $W(x) = \sum a(p) \exp(ipx)$ and $V(x) = \sum V_k \exp(ikx)$. Then:

$$a(p) \frac{p^2}{2m} + \sum_k V_k a(p-k) = E_n a(p) \quad ((1))$$

In other words, impulse collisions occur between the particle and $V(x)$ and so momentum must be identifiable, but any $\exp(ikx) \exp(i(p-k)x$ yields $\exp(ipx)$, but represents different energy. Thus a momentum p is no longer associated with $p^2/2m$. In fact ((1)) shows that any p is identifiable with energy E_n . The $\exp(ipx)$'s interfere so that a new spatial resolution pattern is created and $\exp(-iE_n t)$ represents a resolution in time with a frequency proportional to $1/E_n$.

Different Time Frequencies

We argue that the expression $\exp(-iE_n t)$ is linked to a time resolution $1/E_n$. E_n , however, is linked to an energy interaction due to the particle receiving impulse hits from $V(x)$ and forming a resonance. E_n is binding energy and is only part of the overall rest mass of the M_1, m_2 system with $V(x)$ being produced by M_1 . Thus one really has: $\exp(-i(M_1 + m_2 + E_n)t)$ which implies an overall time resolution of $1/(M_1 + m_2 + E_n)$. Thus there are two frequencies or time resolutions appearing. If E_n goes to 0 i.e. m_2 becomes free then $1/M_1$ is the time resolution of M_1 and $1/m_2$ the time resolution of m_2 suggesting so absolute time even though $\exp(im_2 t) \exp(-m_2 t) = 1$, but rather various different time resolutions or frequencies associated with different energies.

Time Resolution

Just as $\exp(ipx)$'s may interfere, one may have interference of $\exp(-iE_n t)$ terms. In (1) an example is given of an infinite well potential using the first two energy levels and eigenfunctions W_1 and W_2 . W_a and W_b are defined as:

$$W_a = 1/\sqrt{2} \{ W_1 + W_2 \} \text{ and } W_b = 1/\sqrt{2} \{ W_1 - W_2 \} \quad ((2))$$

$$\text{Then: } W(x,t) \text{ is defined as: } 1/\sqrt{2} \{ W_a + W_b \exp(-i \Delta E t) \} \exp(-iE_1 t) \quad ((3))$$

At a given x , one may watch the probability change in time as there is a time resolution or frequency similar to density appearing or disappearing in x for spatial interference.

E_1 and E_2 , however, are linked to well-defined time resolutions $1/E_1$ and $1/E_2$, but the system seems to be interacting with say an outside photon source which allows it to jump from one level to another and then decay so one has interference. It seems that this interaction creates the time resolution which is now explicitly visible as a two slit interference pattern is.

Both of these resolution patterns appear to be strange because classically one expects a particle to have access to all x and t as there is apparently nothing stopping it. The nature of energy and energy flow, however, which governs the particle may be the source of these

intrinsic resolutions in time and space. In other words, energy and momentum may not be simply numbers associated with a particle at a given time or space x, t . Energy and momentum definition may be nonlocal and require regions of time and space linked to resolution or frequencies/wavelengths.

Interactions Altering Time and Spatial Resolutions

As argued above, a free particle has energy and momentum which define its time and spatial resolutions. An interaction may occur which obscures the unique energy of a single particle while retaining its unique momentum. For example, a $V(x)$ has no time component and delivers momentum impulses changing the particle's momentum. In this way one considers the unique p values a particle may have, but an overall E_n is created which establishes a time resolution. The interference of the $\exp(ipx)$'s based on the "unique" p values of the single particle creates spatial resolution.

A particle which is bound by $V(x)$ may have different eigenenergies E_n , but an interaction with outside photons may obscure the identity of the E_n allowing for an interference pattern which creates an overall new time resolution pattern. Thus the idea of spatial and time resolution seem to be linked to momentum and energy and these in turn are linked to interactions. Thus the idea of continuous space and time used in classical mechanics does not seem to be the picture in the quantum world we argue.

Conclusion

In conclusion we argue energy and momentum do not seem to be simply numbers associated with a particle $x(t)$. In particular, momentum and energy by their nature seem to be associated with resolution in space and time i.e. nonlocality. Thus the idea of continuous x and t used in classical mechanics does not seem to be the picture in quantum mechanics even though $\exp(-iEt+ipx) \cdot \exp(-iEt+ipx) = 1$ for a free particle. The underlying resolutions of $1/E$ and $1/p$ are real and manifest themselves giving the sense that a particle is "blocked" from certain points of space or time when this is due to the nature of energy and momentum which are nonlocal in x and t . This nonlocality in terms of space may be seen classically in a wave in a medium. In order to have energy and momentum of the classical wave pass through the medium, nonlocality in space is required (e.g. water wave, sound wave etc). In quantum mechanics energy seems to be linked to resolution, but there is no medium so one requires two dimensions for a free particle i.e. $\cos(px)$ and its shifted $\sin(px)$ to show the motion, but there is the same spatial resolution involved. This may be a property of energy and energy flow which leads to a particle having high probability to be at certain time and spatial points and almost zero at others.

Time resolution like spatial is linked to interactions. If time resolution defines the sense of time, then it seems there is no absolute time in the quantum scenario. Instead one has frequencies or resolution associated with various forms of energy which are usually due to interactions. In other words there is a frequency $1/E_n$ associated with binding energy even though the total energy is $M_1 + m_2 + E_n$ leading to a completely different resolution or frequency. Thus in a sense one does not think of absolute time as one does in classical mechanics.

References

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